

Type-II CdSe/ZnO Core-Shell Nanorods: Nanoheterostructures with a Tunable dual Emission in Visible and Near-Infrared Spectral Ranges

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Abstract. We report a synthesis of luminescent nano-heterostructures consisting of CdSe nanorod (NR) cores and a ZnO shell with up to three monolayers of ZnO. The core/shell heterostructures show a tunable, dual photoluminescence (PL) in visible and NIR spectral ranges. The visible PL band attributed to the carrier recombination within the CdSe core of the heterostructures shifts to lower energy by ~ 0.05 to 0.15 eV relative to the bare CdSe NRs, due to a reduced quantum confinement. A NIR band, observed ~ 0.4 - 0.5 eV below the PL energy of the CdSe core, is attributed to a type-II carrier recombination across the CdSe/ZnO interface. The total PL quantum yield (PLQY) in the brightest heterostructures reaches $\sim 20\%$, which is up to 100-times higher than the PLQY of the corresponding bare CdSe NRs. The average lifetimes of the visible PL in heterostructures can reach ~ 100 ns, compared to ~ 5 ns typical for bare CdSe NRs. The average PL lifetimes attributed to the type-II charge separated states reach or exceed one microsecond. Strong NIR PL, tunable in the 800-900 nm spectral range and the long-lived charge separated state make the CdSe/ZnO core-shell NRs appealing materials for exploitation in applications such as bioimaging, photocatalysis and optoelectronics.

1. Introduction

Colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals (NCs) continue attracting significant research interest thanks to their size- and shape-tunable properties resulting from the quantum confinement effect.^[1] Significant advances in the colloidal syntheses over the past several decades provided means for controlling the size dispersion of the NCs with a precision of few percent and gave access to nanostructures with various shapes, spatially confined in one, two or three dimensions (2D, 1D and 0D materials, respectively).^[2] Quasi-1D nanostructures known as quantum nanorods (NRs) are an important subset of NCs at the boundary between the 0D quantum dots and 1D quantum nanowires. From the fundamental standpoint, NRs represent an interesting platform for investigation of the NC shape effects upon transition from three- to two-dimensional spatial confinement.^[3] Their practical appeal is that they combine good tunability of electronic properties similar to those observed in 0D materials with the appealing properties of 1D structures, such as high absorption cross sections,^[4] linearly polarized photoluminescence (PL),^[5] reduced Auger relaxation dynamics^[6] and good charge transporting properties.^[7] The progress made in the syntheses of 1D nanostructures resulted in NRs with variety of chemical compositions prepared by diverse approaches, such as controlled anisotropic growth, directed attachment, catalyst-assisted growth and others.^[2d, 8] Thanks to these advances, the unique characteristics of NRs could be effectively exploited in applications such as bioimaging^[9], liquid crystals,^[10] lasers,^[5, 11] light emitting diodes (LEDs),^[12] photovoltaics,^[13] and others. In spite of the undeniable practical potential of semiconductor NRs, some notable limitations of these materials are low PL quantum yields and short exciton lifetimes.^[3a, 13a, 14]

More recently, studies of colloidal semiconductor NRs have focused on the development of heterostructures comprising multiple materials with different compositions and/or phases, to address the limitations of NRs and enhance their functionality.^[15] Sophisticated synthetic approaches utilizing epitaxial growth and ion exchange methods are being developed to allow tailoring the functionalities of the NR heterostructures to specific applications by combining two or more materials with distinct chemical compositions, shapes, crystal phases or orientations. Rational exploitation of differences in ligand surface affinities, lattice strain, and alloying led to the development of new materials for enhanced applications in photovoltaics^[16] or LEDs^[17] as well as opportunities in the design of new applications in areas such as photocatalysis,^[18] nanoelectronics,^[19] or optical upconversion.^[20] While new strategies and materials are being developed at a rapid pace, so far, the majority of the prepared NR heterostructures have been based on combining multiple chalcogenides with general composition CdE, ZnE, (E = S, Se, Te),^[15, 21] chalcogenides with noble metals^[22] or with metal

oxide cores.^[23] Drawbacks of many of the prepared materials are the presence of toxic heavy metals in their structure and the limited photochemical stability of chalcogenides.^[24] The development of structures combining chalcogenide NR cores with metal oxide shells could address some of these limitations and lead to introduction of new functionalities. For example, ZnSe/ZnO NRs^[25] showed enhanced photocatalytic activity compared to the ZnSe cores. However, the chalcogenide-oxide NR heterostructures have so far been less explored.

Here we describe the preparation of core-shell heterostructures comprising CdSe NR core and ZnO shell by a two-step colloidal synthesis. Although, the preparation of spherical CdSe/ZnO core/shell quantum dots (QDs) by colloidal synthesis was described previously,^[26] this is the first report describing the preparation of the CdSe/ZnO core/shell NRs. Part of the challenge with the preparation of the core/shell NRs is a lower thermal stability of the NRs relative to the QDs as well as the preferential crystal growth along a single extended axis.^[2a-c] We show that with a careful design of the reaction conditions not only the formation of an ZnO shell on the CdSe NRs is possible, but also that the shell thickness can be varied in a controlled manner. The analysis of the optical properties of the heterostructures reveals that the introduction of the ZnO shell leads to significant changes in their absorption and photoluminescence (PL) properties, dramatic enhancement of the PL quantum yield and excited state lifetimes and appearance of NIR PL, which we attribute to type-II carrier recombination. Although type-II NR heterostructures were described previously,^[21, 23] the preparation of type-II NR heterostructure with a ZnO shell has not yet been reported.

2. Results and Discussion

The core CdSe NRs were synthesized by reaction of Cd-TDPA (TDPA = tetradecylphosphonic acid) with TOP-Se (TOP = trioctylphosphine) at 260 °C under an Argon atmosphere by a method described by Shieh *et al.*^[27] The diameter (d) and the length (l) of the NRs were controlled by the number of TOP-Se injections into the reaction mixture. Prior to the shelling reaction, the CdSe NRs were washed in chloroform and re-precipitated in methanol, to remove the excess ligands. The synthetic approach used in the preparation of the CdSe/ZnO NRs is graphically summarized in **Scheme 1**. The purified CdSe NR cores were heated to 60 °C in deaerated 1-octadecene (ODE) and Oleic Acid (OA) under Argon. Separately, Zn(acac)₂ was dissolved in deaerated Oleylamine (OLAm) and ODE under Argon. The preheated (60 °C) solution containing Zn(acac)₂ (acac = acetylacetonate) was injected into the solution containing the CdSe NR cores. The temperature of the mixture was then gradually increased to 230 °C and held at this temperature for at least 30 min. Additional details are given in the methods section.

Scheme 1. Synthetic approach used in the coating of ZnO shell onto the CdSe Nanorods.

Fig. 1(a)-(d) shows representative High-Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and high-resolution STEM (HR-STEM) images of the CdSe NRs cores with an average diameter $\langle d \rangle = 4.1\text{ nm}$ (panels (a) and (b)), and the reaction product, CdSe/ZnO core-shell NRs (panels (c) and (d)). In the image shown in the panel (d), the formation of the ZnO shell can be seen as a white/gray corona on the surface of the light brown NRs with clearly visible lattice fringes. This corona is absent in the image of the CdSe cores (panel (b)). As can be seen in the high-resolution image, the ZnO shell forms relatively uniformly around the CdSe core with a similar shell thickness seen for all NRs. This observation is consistent with the more systematic statistical analysis of the diameter and length distributions of the NRs before and after shelling, summarized in **Fig. 1(e)-(h)**. Based on the analysis, the overcoating with the ZnO shell resulted in an average increase of the NR volume by 1.7 nm and length by 6.2 nm. The corresponding volume increase of 178 nm^3 is in a reasonable agreement with the value of 157 nm^3 calculated based on the amount of added Zn(acac)_2 precursor (see discussion below). Despite the substantial size increase, the aspect

Figure 1. HAADF STEM images of CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 4.1\text{ nm}$) before (a, b) and after (c, d) ZnO shell growth. The amount of the Zn(acac)_2 precursor used in the reaction corresponded to 3 ML of ZnO (see methods section). Diameter, d , and length, l , histograms of the CdSe NRs before shelling (e, f) and the product core/shell CdSe/ZnO NRs (g, h), obtained from the analysis of the probe-corrected HR-STEM images. Each histogram was generated by analysis of the images of at least one hundred NRs.

ratio of the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures ($AR = l/d = 11 \pm 3$) remained similar with the CdSe core ($AR = 9 \pm 2$). The STEM images and the statistical analysis of the other NR sizes, showing similar results, are summarized in SI, **Fig. S1-S3** and **Table TS4**.

The prepared CdSe NRs and the heterostructures were further characterized by the Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) elemental mapping. The 1D structure of the NRs could be observed clearly in the HAADF-STEM images, as shown in **Fig. 2(a)**. The elemental mapping of Cd and Se of the core NRs presented in **Fig. 2 (b)** and (c), shows a homogeneous distribution of Cd and Se in all NRs. Panels (d)-(g) in **Fig. 2** show similar elemental mapping of CdSe/ZnO heterostructures, where Cd, Se, and Zn are indicated by yellow, orange, and green color, respectively. In the maps, a distinct signal corresponding to Zn (panel (g)) is observed, concentrated in the same areas as the maxima of the signals for Cd and Se, indicating formation of a ZnO shell on the CdSe NRs (see also **Fig. S3, S7** and **TS5** in SI). Overall, the results summarized in **Fig. 1** and **2** show that the reaction of CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm) with $Zn(acac)_2$ under the conditions summarized in **Scheme 1**, yields CdSe/ZnO NR core-shell nano-heterostructures. Similar results were obtained for CdSe NRs of other sizes (see SI).

To better understand the mechanism of the ZnO shell formation, growth solution aliquots were collected at various stages of the reaction and characterized by UV-VIS absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopies. The spectra collected during the shelling reaction of the CdSe NRs cores with the average diameter $\langle d \rangle = 4.7$ nm are shown in **Fig. 3**. As shown in panel (a), a distinct excitonic peak is observed in the absorption spectra of CdSe NRs at ~ 575 - 599 nm in all aliquots. During the reaction, the maximum of the peak shifts from 575 nm for the NR core to 599 nm for the aliquot measured at the end of the reaction (30 min.). An increase

Figure 2. HAADF STEM images and corresponding EDS elemental maps of CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm (a-c) and the core-shell CdSe/ZnO NRs (d-g) prepared by reaction summarized in Scheme 1. In the color element mapping Cd, Se, and Zn are indicated by yellow, orange, and green colors, respectively.

Figure 3. Investigation of the mechanism of the ZnO shell growth on the CdSe NRs. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 4.7$ nm) and the growth solution aliquots collected at indicated temperatures and reaction times, following the addition of the $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ precursor corresponding to 3 ML of ZnO. The aliquots were prepared by suspending 100 μl of growth solution in 3 ml of *n*-hexane. All spectra were normalized at the maximum of the first excitonic peak at ~ 575 -590 nm and were slightly offset for clarity. (b) PL spectra of the same series of aliquots. The excitation wavelength was 385 nm.

in the absorption at the wavelengths below 400 nm, relative to the absorption of the CdSe NR cores is notable in all spectra. This is consistent with the formation of ZnO, which has an onset of absorption at ~ 370 -400 nm (**Fig. S9**).^[26]

The PL spectrum of the CdSe NR cores (NRs in **Fig. 3(b)**) shows a single peak at 599 nm, attributed to the band edge radiative carrier recombination. Similar peak is observed in all aliquots, but its position gradually shifts to 619 nm by the end of the reaction (30 min in **Fig. 3(b)**). There is also a new, broad, and intense peak with maximum near 800 nm observed in all spectra. In the aliquots collected at 150 °C and 200 °C, additional peaks are observed near 525 nm and 540 nm, respectively, which gradually disappear, once the reaction temperature is increased to 230 °C. The appearance of these high-energy peaks is consistent with the formation of a population of ZnO NCs. As was reported previously,^[26, 28] (and also observed for ZnO NCs independently synthesized here; **Fig. S9**), the PL spectra of ZnO NCs typically include two main features; a narrow band at ~ 385 nm, attributed to the radiative band-edge carrier (electron-hole) recombination and a broader PL feature in the 450-550 nm spectral range, attributed to the recombination of an electron at, or near the conduction band, with a hole at a defect site, associated with an oxygen vacancy. The position and the intensity of the low energy peak depend on the NC size as well as the solvent and ligand environment.^[29] Our observations thus suggest that at the intermediate temperatures 150 °C and 200 °C an independent population of ZnO NCs forms alongside the core CdSe NRs, as shown graphically in the middle part of the

Scheme 1. At the same time, some of the $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ precursor converts to a thin ZnO shell on the surface of CdSe NRs, as indicated by a noticeable red shift of the peak near 600 nm and an appearance of the new broad PL band near 800 nm. With a further increase in the temperature to 230 °C, the ZnO NCs gradually dissolve, and the released monomers deposit on the surfaces of the CdSe NRs, to complete the ZnO shell formation. This is observed as a further shift in the 600 nm band and a growth and a red shift of the band near 800 nm. The electronic origins of these spectral changes are discussed in more detail in the following sections.

The mechanism of the ZnO shell growth proposed above is consistent also with a HR STEM analysis summarized in **Fig. S4** and **S5**. The images show that in some reactions ZnO NCs, independent and partially fused with the CdSe NRs, as well as partially shelled CdSe NRs can be detected in the product mixture. A Fourier transform analysis of the images confirmed the presence of the ZnO crystalline planes. However, a closer inspection shows that the signal from the crystalline ZnO is primarily located in the regions containing the spheroidal ZnO NCs fused with the CdSe NRs, while the ZnO shells show no crystalline character. We attribute the lack of crystallinity of the ZnO shell to a relatively low growth temperature (230 °C) (used to prevent the decomposition of the CdSe NR cores) combined with a significant lattice mismatch between the CdSe core and the ZnO shell.^[26]

To better understand the effect of the ZnO shell growth on the electronic structure of the NRs, we synthesized a series of CdSe/ZnO core/shell heterostructures with the average diameter of the core $\langle d \rangle = 3.2, 4.1$ and 4.7 nm, modified with 3 ML of ZnO shell, and characterized them by electronic absorption and PL spectroscopies. The results are summarized in **Fig. 4**. The figure shows the optical absorption spectra, steady-state PL, and PL decay dynamics recorded for the bare CdSe NRs and the corresponding CdSe/ZnO core/shell heterostructures.

The electronic absorption spectra (panel (a)) show that the overcoating of the CdSe NRs by ZnO shell leads to a noticeable red shift of the low-energy excitonic peak near 535-600 nm. The shift is most pronounced for the thinnest ($\langle d \rangle = 3.2$) NRs. In all spectra of the heterostructures there is an increase in the absorption below 400 nm, consistent with the ZnO formation. The PL spectra (panel (b)) of the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures (red traces) are distinctly different from the spectra of the corresponding bare CdSe NRs (blue traces). While the bare NRs show only one PL band near 550-600 nm (blue shading), the heterostructures show dual PL with one PL band in the region 580-650 nm (red shading) and another, more pronounced band with a peak around 800-850 nm (magenta shading). We attribute the PL bands

Figure 4. Comparison of the optical properties of the CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2, 4.1$ and 4.7 nm, before and after ZnO shelling. In all cases the amount of the $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ precursor used in the shelling reaction corresponded to 3 ML of ZnO. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the bare CdSe NRs (blue traces) and the corresponding CdSe/ZnO core/shell heterostructures (red traces). All spectra were normalized at the first excitonic peak. The spectra for different sizes of NRs are offset for clarity. (b) PL spectra of the bare CdSe NRs (blue trace, blue shading) and the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures (red trace), divided into a high energy region (light red shading) and a low energy region, (magenta shading). All spectra were normalized at the band edge peak in the 550–650 nm range (the normalization factors are shown in the figure). The PL spectra were collected using the excitation wavelength of 385 nm. (c) Time-dependent PL decays. The decays were recorded at the corresponding peak maxima in the 550–650 nm range for the bare CdSe NRs (blue traces) and the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures (red traces). The decays of the NIR PL of the CdSe/ZnO NRs (magenta traces) were collected at the corresponding PL maxima in the 800–850 nm range. All decays were normalized at time = 0 ns. The PL decays were collected using the excitation wavelength of 402 nm, with the excitation energy of $6.4 \text{ nJ/pulse.cm}^2$. All spectra were collected at room temperature on samples suspended in *n*-hexane.

near 550–600 nm for both the bare CdSe NRs and the core/shell heterostructures to a radiative recombination of the carriers within the CdSe. The peak positions for this transition are in heterostructures shifted to lower energies, similarly to the low energy peaks in the absorption spectra (panel (a)). The PL intensities of the peaks associated with the carrier recombination within CdSe are in the heterostructures dramatically enhanced (~ 3 -, 8- and ~ 11 -times for CdSe/ZnO NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2, 4.1$ and 4.7 , respectively), relative to the corresponding bare CdSe NRs. (Note: To show the spectral shifts more clearly, the PL spectra of the heterostructures in **Fig. 4(b)** were scaled down so that the PL peak of the bare CdSe and the low-energy PL peak of the corresponding CdSe/ZnO heterostructure have the same intensity. The scaling factors shown in the Figure, correspond to $0.33 = 1/3$, $0.12 = 1/8$ and $0.09 = 1/11$). As explained in more detail below, the new dominant peak near 800–850 nm in the spectra of the heterostructures is

attributed to a type-II radiative carrier recombination across the CdSe/ZnO interface. In the spectra shown in the **Fig. 4(b)**, this feature is broader and for $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ and 4.7 , much more intense than the corresponding CdSe “core” PL for the same heterostructure. When accounting for both the visible and NIR features, the overall PL quantum yields (PLQYs) of the heterostructures with the core diameter $\langle d \rangle = 3.2, 4.1$ and 4.7 nm are 10.6%, 6.1% and 18.9%, respectively, compared to the 1.8%, 0.17% and 0.17% PLQYs observed for the corresponding bare CdSe NRs. That means ~6-, 40- and 110-fold enhancement of the PLQY as a result of introducing of the ZnO shell (see **TS6**).

A comparison of the PL decays in **Fig. 4(c)** shows that the relaxation dynamics of the exciton measured near 600 nm is significantly slower in the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures (red traces) than the corresponding relaxation dynamics of the bare CdSe NRs (blue traces). A fit of the PL decays with a multiexponential expression yielded average excited state lifetimes in the range of 5-30 ns for the bare NRs and 65-103 ns for the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures. The relaxation dynamics of the NIR PL of the heterostructures (magenta traces) are still much slower. The analysis of the relaxation dynamics of the PL in the 800 - 850 nm range yielded the average excited state lifetimes of 1.0, 1.4 and 1.4 μ s for the heterostructures with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2, 4.1$ and 4.7 nm, respectively (see **TS7**).

In a separate experiment, we synthesized a series of CdSe/ZnO core/shell heterostructures with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm NR cores overcoated with 1, 5 and 7 monolayers of the ZnO shell. The diameter and length histograms obtained from the analysis of the TEM images (see **Fig. S6**) of the bare CdSe NR starting materials and the core/shell structures are shown in **Fig. 5 (a)-(h)**. Theoretically predicted and the experimental volumes determined from the histograms (**Fig. 5 i**) show a good agreement up to the 3 ML of ZnO. For the 5- and 7-ML shells the volume increase observed experimentally is below the theoretically predicted volume increase. An inspection of the data in panels (a)-(h) shows that for the heterostructures with 5 and 7 ML there is no significant increase in their thickness, only a moderate increase in their length. The aspect ratio of all the heterostructures is, within the experimental error, the same as the aspect ratio of the corresponding bare CdSe NRs. Similar results were observed for heterostructures with the core diameters $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ and 4.7 nm.

The optical properties of the same series of heterostructures are summarized in **Fig. 6**. The absorption spectra in panel (a), show that as the thickness of the ZnO shell increases, the band-edge absorption peak shifts from 535 to 570 nm (shift of ~0.13 eV), with a notable increase in the absorbance in the range below 400 nm, reflecting the ZnO formation. The PL spectra in

Figure 5. Diameter, d , and length, l , histograms of the CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm, before shelling (a, b) and after overcoating with one (c, d) five (e, f) and seven (g, h) monolayers of ZnO shell. Panel (i) shows a comparison of the theoretically calculated volume of the CdSe/ZnO NRs, based on the amount of precursor used, and the corresponding experimental volumes determined from the TEM analysis summarized in panels (a)-(h). The experimental value for 3 ML of ZnO was determined from data shown in Fig. S1.

panel (b) show the dual PL of the core/shell heterostructures similar to the spectra shown in Fig. 4(b). The high energy peak attributed to the radiative recombination at the CdSe core increases in intensity with increasing thickness of the ZnO shell and shows a spectral shift similar to the absorption, from 552 nm to 588 nm (~ 0.14 eV). A smaller shift, ~ 617 to 635 nm (0.08 eV), was observed for the NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm (Fig. S8, TS6, TS9). The NIR PL does

Figure 6. Dependence of the optical properties of the CdSe/ZnO NRs on the ZnO shell thickness, with the CdSe NR core average diameter $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm and the ZnO shell thickness of 0, 1, 5 and 7 ML. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra in *n*-hexane. Inset shows the photographs of the solutions of the same samples under ambient light (top) and excited with 365 nm UV light (bottom). (b) The PL spectra of the same materials. The excitation wavelength was 385 nm. (c) Time-dependent PL decays for the same samples as shown in panels (a) and (b). The “core” decays for the bare CdSe and the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures were collected at the corresponding band-edge peak maxima near 550-600 nm. The NIR PL decays (type-II) of the CdSe/ZnO NRs were collected at the corresponding PL maxima. All decays were normalized at time = 0 ns. The PL decays were collected using the excitation wavelength of 402 nm, with excitation energy of 6.4 nJ/pulse.cm². All spectra were collected at room temperature using NRs suspended in hexanes. (d) Summary of the variations in the PL peak position for CdSe NRs (0 ML) and CdSe/ZnO NRs (1, 3, 5, and 7 ML of ZnO) for the visible PL (solid circles) and NIR PL (open circles) for core NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm (black), 4.1 nm (red), and 4.7 nm (blue). The average lifetimes for the same series of materials are presented by solid and open triangles for the visible and the NIR PL, respectively.

not show significant change in the intensity, but it gradually shifts from ~ 770 to ~ 800 with increasing shell thickness (**Fig. 6, TS8, TS9**). These results are consistent with the results of the PL lifetime measurements summarized in panel (c). The PL relaxation dynamics monitored at the visible peak gradually slows down with the increasing number of ZnO monolayers. The PL relaxation dynamics monitored in the NIR yields an average lifetime of ~ 1 μ s, increasing slightly with the shell thickness.

Panel (d) shows a summary of the observed spectral shifts (circles) as well as the variation in the average lifetimes (triangles) of the visible (solid symbols) and the NIR (empty symbols) PL. The results show that the most notable spectral shifts are observed upon introduction of the

first three monolayers of the ZnO. This is consistent with the observations summarized in Fig. 5i. Similar trends are observed for the average lifetimes.

The results summarized in **Figs. 4** and **6** can be explained using the energy diagram shown in **Scheme 2** (a), (b). In the photoexcited CdSe NRs the charge carriers (electron and the hole) are confined within the nanoparticle (panel (a)).^[30] In bare NCs, without an inorganic shell, the wavefunctions of the carriers can sample defects on the CdSe surface, which can promote a surface-mediated exciton relaxation, reducing PLQY and accelerating PL relaxation dynamics.^[31] In the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures (panel (b)), the ZnO shell can passivate the defects on the surface of the CdSe core, increase the PL lifetime and PLQY. This is consistent with our observation of ~3-10-fold increase in the visible PLQY and up to ~100-fold increase in the overall PLQY (**Fig. 4** (b), **TS6**).

In addition to passivating the surface defects, an introduction of an inorganic shell can also lead to formation of a type-II interface. Formation of type-II (or quasi-type II) interface in core/shell nanoheterostructures was observed previously in materials such as CdSe/CdS,^[31] CdTe/CdSe and CdSe/ZnTe,^[32] CdS/ZnSe,^[33] InP/CdSe^[34] QDs as well as CdSe/CdTe NRs.^[21e, 35] The possibility of formation of type-II interface in CdSe/ZnO nanoheterostructures has been

Scheme 2. Simplified band alignment diagram for: (a) CdSe NRs and (b) core-shell CdSe/ZnO NRs. The red and blue shaded areas in the bottom part of the diagram represent the electron and hole wavefunctions, respectively. The E_{conf} is a confinement energy, Abs is the absorption, PL is the photoluminescence, NR represents a nonradiative decay via surface defects. The red and the blue dashed areas represent the surface defects. The R ($= d/2$) and H are the radius of the CdSe NR and the thickness of the ZnO shell, respectively. The wide gray arrows indicate the direction of the heterostructure expansion due to the increase in R and/or H . (c) Alignment of the band energies at the CdSe QD/ZnO film interface as a function of CdSe QD size based on the UV photoelectron studies of CdSe QDs/ZnO film interfaces. Adapted from ref. 36.

proposed previously.^[36] For the type-II interface to form, the conduction and valence bands of the core and the shell materials have to be arranged in a staggered alignment. Although ZnO has a significantly larger bandgap ($E_{g,bulk} \sim 3.3$ eV)^[37] than CdSe ($E_{g,bulk} \sim 1.74$ eV), previous studies of CdSe QD/ZnO film interfaces by Carlson, *et. al.*^[38] and later by Li, *et. al.*^[39] showed that the conduction band edge offsets for the two materials are close in energy. Both studies showed that CdSe QDs/ZnO film structures can form type-II interface, with the extent of the type-II character varying with the QD size. The studies also showed that the alignment of the band offsets depends on the nature of the CdSe/ZnO interface. In case of strong electronic interactions between the CdSe and ZnO (as expected for the CdSe/ZnO NR studied here), the type-II character of the interface increases with the QD size (Scheme 2 (c)).^[39] Given the similarities of the electronic structures of the CdSe QDs and NRs,^[40] the results of Li *et. al.*, are considered to be a good approximation of the band alignments at the interface in the CdSe/ZnO NRs studied here.

One effect of the formation of the type-II interface in the CdSe/ZnO NRs is that it allows delocalization of the photoexcited electron across the CdSe/ZnO interface (with the hole primarily confined within the CdSe core). The reduced electron confinement results in lowering of the energy of the excited state ($E_g^I < E_g(\text{CdSe NR})$ in **Scheme 2(a),(b)**). This is experimentally observed as a small (50-150 meV) red shift in the band edge absorption and the “core” PL, observed for all CdSe/ZnO NRs in the visible spectral range 550-650 nm. (**Figs. 4(a),(b) and 6(a), (b) and (d), TS6.**). In addition, in the heterostructures with thin CdSe cores and thin ZnO shells (small R and H , in **Scheme 2(b)**), the electron wavefunction could extend to sample the defects at the surface of the ZnO layer. In such cases adding additional passivating layers of ZnO can lead to increase in the visible PL intensity. This is consistent with our observation of increase in the visible PL intensity with increasing shell thickness in heterostructures with CdSe core with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm (**Fig. 6 (b)**).

Similar arguments can be used to explain the slower visible PL relaxation dynamics in the heterostructures, compared to the bare CdSe. Passivation of the surface defects by introduction of the ZnO shell reduces the contribution of the nonradiative relaxation channels, which results in longer average lifetimes. In addition, an extension of the electron wavefunction into the ZnO shell, reduces the electron-hole wavefunction overlap, resulting in a smaller radiative recombination rate,^[41] which can further increase the observed average lifetime. We attribute the observed increase in the average lifetime of visible PL by factor of $\sim 3-15$ (**TS7**) to the combination of these two effects.

The deposition of the ZnO shell can also create new radiative relaxation channels that are responsible for the observation of the intense NIR PL with slow relaxation dynamics (**Figs. 4(b), (c) and 6(b), (c)**). One possibility is that the shell deposition introduces new defects, where the electron and hole can effectively recombine radiatively with slow recombination dynamics. Although, the exact structure of the CdSe/ZnO interface is not known and formation of defects is possible, several systematic studies of defect-based emission in CdSe (and CdTe) NCs^[42] have shown that the average lifetimes of defect-related emission in these materials do not typically exceed 300 ns. These studies also showed that as the relative contribution of the defect-related relaxation increases, the overall quantum yield of the PL typically decreases. This is contrary to our observations for CdSe/ZnO NRs, where the detection of low energy PL, with lifetime $\geq 1 \mu\text{s}$ is associated with up to 100-fold increase in the PLQY.

Another possibility is that the electron deposition of the ZnO shell opens a new type-II relaxation channel (PL_{II} in **Scheme 2** (b)) allowing for recombination of the electron delocalized into the ZnO shell with the CdSe core localized hole, at the energy $E_g^{II} < E_g^I$. Based on the results reported by Li *et. al.*,^[39] for CdSe QD/ZnO film interfaces the type-II recombination is expected in the energy range of $\sim 1.3 - 1.7 \text{ eV}$ or $\sim 730 - 950 \text{ nm}$. This is in a good agreement with our observations of the new NIR PL for CdSe/ZnO NRs with the peaks in the range $\sim 770 - 880 \text{ nm}$ (**Fig. 4(b), TS6, TS8, TS9**). Because of the low wavefunction overlap between the core localized hole and the electron delocalized into the ZnO shell, the type-II relaxation dynamics is expected to be significantly slower than the carrier recombination within the CdSe core.^[41] This is consistent with the observation of a slow relaxation dynamics of the NIR PL in CdSe/ZnO NRs, with average lifetimes of $\sim 1 - 1.4 \mu\text{s}$ (**Fig. 4 (c), TS7**). Based on these observations, we attribute the NIR PL observed in CdSe/ZnO NRs to the type-II recombination.

As discussed above, the results of Carlson, *et. al.*^[38] and Li, *et. al.*^[39] show that the nature of the CdSe/ZnO interface can play an important role in determining the electronic alignment of the CdSe and ZnO band offsets. In addition, as was shown in previous studies of CdS/ZnSe^[33] and InP/CdSe^[34] core/shell QDs, optical properties of the type-II heterostructures are determined not only by the band offsets of the comprising materials, but also by the nature of the core/shell interface and the quality of the shell. Both are sensitive to the preparation conditions and can lead to significant variations in the intensities of the type-II PL as well as observation of dual visible and NIR PL.^[34] Further studies aimed at better understanding of the effect of interface on the optical properties of the CdSe/ZnO heterostructures are currently in progress.

3. Conclusions

We have synthesized CdSe/ZnO NR core/shell heterostructures using a two-step colloidal synthesis. We show that the thickness of the shell can be controlled by the amount of the added Zn precursor up to 3 ML of ZnO and that the aspect ratio of the NRs is retained after the shell growth. The introduction of the shell leads to formation of a type-II NR heterostructure. The formation of type-II interface has a significant effect on the electronic structure and optical properties of the NRs, including: shifts in the visible absorption and PL, more than 100-fold increase in the overall PLQY \sim 20%, and a formation of a long-lived charge separated state. The heterostructures are stable for months when stored in *n*-hexane under ambient conditions. The combination of stability, long-lived charge separated state and high quantum yields makes the CdSe/ZnO NRs attractive materials for use in optoelectronic devices and energy conversion applications. High PL quantum yields and tunability of the emission in the 800-900 nm spectral range, combined with a reduced toxicity and good stability of CdSe/ZnO heterostructures in biological media,^[43] are appealing features for exploitation of these structures in bioimaging applications.^[44]

4. Experimental Methods

Chemicals and materials: Cadmium oxide (CdO, 99.95%, Sigma-Aldrich), selenium powder (Se, 99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), zinc acetylacetonate ($\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$, Sigma Aldrich), oleylamine (OLAm, technical grade 70%, Sigma-Aldrich), oleic acid (OA, 90% Sigma Aldrich), ethanol (99.8%, Emplura), 1-octadecene (ODE, technical grade 90%, Sigma Aldrich), *n*-hexane (95%, Emplura), trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich), trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO, 90%, Sigma-Aldrich), *n*-tetradecylphosphonic acid (TDPA, 98%, Alfa Aesar), acetone (99.5%, Mikrochem), chloroform (99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), methanol (99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), tributylphosphine (TBP, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich) were all used as received from the supplier, without further purification.

Synthesis of CdSe NRs: 0.2 mol/L of TOP-Se solution was prepared at ambient temperature inside an argon-filled glovebox by dissolving Se powder in stirred trioctylphosphine (TOP). The cadmium precursor, Cd-TDPA, was prepared by dissolving 0.114 g CdO (0.89 mmol) and 0.43 g *n*-tetradecylphosphonic acid (TDPA) (0.16 mmol) in 7 g of stirred (using glass stir-bar) 90 % trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO) deaerated by applying vacuum, followed by flushing with argon, three times at 65 °C, and once at 120 °C. The mixture was then heated to 340 °C under argon. Above 300 °C, the color of solution gradually turned from dark red to white, indicating the formation of the Cd-TDPA complex. The solution was then cooled down to 260

°C. To generate the CdSe NRs, 0.5 mL of 0.2 mol/L concentrated TOP-Se was repeatedly rapidly injected through a septum into the reaction flask in 3-minute intervals. The size of the NRs was varied by the number of TOP-Se injections (6 - 8). 3 minutes after the last injection, the heating mantle was removed and the reaction flask was allowed to cool down in air bath. The NRs were purified by dispersing the growth solution in chloroform, precipitating the particles with excess methanol, followed by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 5 min. After the supernatant decantation the NRs were suspended in *n*-hexane for further characterization. In case of samples used for TEM characterization, tributylphosphine (TBP) was added to methanol (v(TBP)/v(MeOH) = 10/90%), to remove the excess unreacted selenium.

Preparation of 0.1 M of Zn precursor: A mixture of 264 mg Zn(acac)₂, 1.316 mL (Oleylamine) OLAm (Zn/OLAm ratio 1:3), and 8.67 mL ODE in a three neck, round-bottom flask was kept at 80 °C under vacuum for 20 min. Upon reaching 50 °C, the solution became clear. The solution was then kept at 60 °C under argon for shell deposition.

Calculation for Zn precursor needed for ZnO shell formation: Step 1: The average length and diameter of the CdSe and CdSe/ZnO NRs were determined from TEM images. The volume of the NRs was calculated by approximating them as perfect cylinders:

$$V_0 = \pi r_0^2 l_0$$

where, r_0 and l_0 are the radius and length of a NR, respectively.

Step 2. The concentration of CdSe NRs were calculated using Lambert-Beer's law:

$$A = cd\varepsilon$$

where, A is absorbance, d is path length, and ε is the molar absorption coefficient. The values of ε were estimated using an empirical relationship between the value of ε at 350 nm (ε_{350}) and NR volume V in cm³, determined previously by Banin et al.:^[4]

$$\varepsilon_{350}(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}) = 0.38 \times 10^{26} V$$

Following the absorption measurement, the number of NRs in solution can be calculated from the known concentration and volume of the CdSe NRs solution.

Step 3. Theoretical calculation of the volume of the core/shell NR. Assuming ZnO shell grows on the surface of the CdSe NRs uniformly, then the radius, r_n , and the length, l_n , of the CdSe/ZnO NR with “ n ” monolayers of ZnO can be calculated as:

$$r_n = r_0 + na_{\text{ZnO}}; l_n = l_0 + na_{\text{ZnO}}; V_n = \pi r_n^2 l_n$$

where $a = 0.325$ nm, the lattice parameter of ZnO.

Step 4. Calculation of volume of Zn (II) precursor needed for growth of desired number of ZnO monolayers. The volume of the ZnO shell can be calculated as:

$$V_{ZnO} = V_n - V_0$$

The mass of ZnO shell was calculated using density $\rho(\text{ZnO}) = 5.61 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and converted to number of moles of ZnO. Since this value corresponds to a single NR, it was multiplied by the total number of CdSe NRs in solution. The number of moles of ZnO was considered to be equal to the number of moles of $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$. Finally, the required volume of the Zn(II) precursor was determined as the ratio of required number of moles and the known concentration of the precursor.

Synthesis of CdSe/ZnO core/shell heterostructures: The purified CdSe NRs (for amounts see **TS1-TS3**) were dispersed in 3 mL ODE in a three-neck round-bottom flask, followed by addition of 0.5 mL of OA. The solution was evacuated at 60 °C for 30 min and the flask was filled with Ar. Subsequently, the Zn precursor (pre-heated to 60 °C) was quickly injected into the reaction mixture. The amounts of Zn precursor used in the preparation of specific ZnO shell thickness are shown in **TS1-TS3**. The reaction temperature was increased to 230 °C and maintained at this temperature for 30 min., to grow the ZnO shell. The heating mantle was then removed and the growth solution was allowed to cool down in air to room temperature. To remove the excess unreacted Zn precursor, the growth solution was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 3 min, followed by decantation of the liquid phase. In a second purification step, the CdSe/ZnO NRs were suspended in small amount of *n*-hexane, precipitated in ethanol/acetone (v/v 1:1) followed by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 5 min. The precipitated NRs were dispersed in *n*-hexane for further characterization.

Synthesis of ZnO nanocrystals: Synthesis of ZnO NCs was done by adapting protocol described previously.^[26] Briefly, 0.5 mmol of $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ was mixed with 21.5 mmol of oleylamine, 115 mmol of 1-octadecene and 0.24 mmol of Oleic acid. The stirred mixture was deaerated by three vacuum/argon cycles at room temperature and once at 80 °C. The mixture was then heated to 270 °C and maintained at this temperature for 60 min. Crystal growth was quenched by removing the heating mantle. Nanocrystals were precipitated from growth solution by addition of excess of acetone/ethanol (v/v 1:1) mixture and isolated by centrifugation (6000 rpm, 5 min). Precipitate was redispersed in *n*-hexane for characterization.

Transmission electron microscopy: Structural characterization and elemental analysis of the NRs were carried out using a cold-field-emission spherical-aberration-corrected analytical transmission electron microscope JEM-ARM 200cF (JEOL, Japan) operated at 200 kV and

equipped with 100 mm² silicon drift-detector JED-2300 (JEOL, Japan) for EDS spectroscopy. The NRs dispersed in *n*-hexane solution were deposited on 400 mesh Au TEM grid covered with ultra-thin carbon/Lacey film using a drop-casting method and dried under IR lamp for 10 minutes.

Optical spectroscopy: Electronic absorption spectra were collected using an Agilent 8453 UV-VIS diode array spectrophotometer. The photoluminescence spectra were recorded using a Fluoromax 3 plus spectrofluorometer (Horiba) equipped with a Hamamatsu R13456 red-sensitive photomultiplier tube. The time-resolved PL decays were collected using a time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) Delta Diode system (Horiba) using a pulsed laser diode (402 nm) with the repetition rate of 1 MHz, pump power 50 μ W and probe beam diameter of 1 mm. The FWHM of the instrument response function was 50 ps. The NRs were dispersed in *n*-hexane and all the spectra were collected in solution.

Determination of the PL quantum yield: The PL quantum yields (PLQY) were determined using a relative measurement method, with Rhodamine 101 as a reference. The excitation wavelength was 385 nm, and the PLQY of Rhodamine 101 was assumed to be 100%. The absorbances of the NRs solutions and the Rhodamine 101 solution at the excitation wavelengths were less than 0.1. The PLQY was calculated as:

$$\varphi_S = \varphi_R \times \frac{I_S}{I_R} \times \frac{A_R}{A_S} \times \frac{\eta_S}{\eta_R}$$

Here, *S* stands for the sample, *R* is a reference, φ is the quantum yield, *I* is the integrated area of the emission spectrum, and η is the refractive index of the solvent. The solvent for the NRs was *n*-hexane ($\eta = 1.39$), and for the Rhodamine 101, ethanol ($\eta = 1.36$). The PL spectra of the CdSe/ZnO core-shell NRs were collected up to 920 nm, a detection limit of our instrument. All spectra were corrected for the spectrometer response using a manufacturer provided correction factors. In cases when the PL spectra did not reach the baseline to this wavelength, the low energy (type-II) peak was fit with a single Gaussian function. The integrated area under the entire Gaussian was included in the calculation of the PLQY.

Analysis of the PL dynamics: The PL decays were analyzed using a following multiexponential expression:

$$I(t) = \sum_i a_i \exp(-t/\tau_i) \quad i = 1, 3,$$

where, a_i and τ_i are the relative contribution and the lifetime of the *i*-th component. The average lifetime was calculated using the expression:

$$\langle \tau \rangle = \frac{\sum_i a_i \tau_i^2}{\sum_i a_i \tau_i} \quad i = 1, 3,$$

where $\langle \tau \rangle$ is the average lifetime.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Author Contributions

A.H.: Conceptualization, materials syntheses, characterization, data analysis, visualization, original manuscript co-writing. F. Z.: Conceptualization, materials syntheses, visualization, original manuscript co-writing. V.V. Materials characterization, data analysis, visualization. M.R. Materials characterization, data analysis. M.S. Conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, original manuscript writing, data analysis, visualization, original manuscript co-writing. The manuscript was edited by all authors.

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References

- [1] a) M. V. Kovalenko, L. Manna, A. Cabot, Z. Hens, D. V. Talapin, C. R. Kagan, V. I. Klimov, A. L. Rogach, P. Reiss, D. J. Milliron, *ACS nano* **2015**, 9, 1012; b) M. A. El-

- Sayed, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2004**, 37, 326; c) W. E. Buhro, V. L. Colvin, *Nature Materials* **2003**, 2, 138; d) A. P. Alivisatos, *Science* **1996**, 271, 933.
- [2] a) Y. Yin, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nature* **2005**, 437, 664; b) L. Manna, E. C. Scher, A. P. Alivisatos, *J. Cluster Sci.* **2002**, 13, 521; c) Z. A. Peng, X. Peng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, 123, 1389; d) X. Peng, L. Manna, W. Yang, J. Wickham, E. Scher, A. Kadavanich, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nature* **2000**, 404, 59; e) C. B. Murray, C. R. Kagan, M. G. Bawendi, *Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci.* **2000**, 30, 545.
- [3] a) A. Shabaev, A. L. Efros, *Nano Lett.* **2004**, 4, 1821; b) H. Yu, J. Li, R. A. Loomis, P. C. Gibbons, Wang, W. E. Buhro, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, 125, 16168; c) L.-s. Li, J. Hu, W. Yang, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nano Lett.* **2001**, 1, 349; d) D. Katz, T. Wizansky, O. Millo, E. Rothenberg, T. Mokari, U. Banin, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2002**, 89, 086801.
- [4] E. Shaviv, A. Salant, U. Banin, *ChemPhysChem* **2009**, 10, 1028.
- [5] M. Kazes, D. Y. Lewis, Y. Ebenstein, T. Mokari, U. Banin, *Adv. Mater.* **2002**, 14, 317.
- [6] J. Yang, B.-R. Hyun, A. J. Basile, F. W. Wise, *ACS Nano* **2012**, 6, 8120.
- [7] a) M. Schierhorn, S. W. Boettcher, J. H. Peet, E. Matioli, G. C. Bazan, G. D. Stucky, M. Moskovits, *ACS Nano* **2010**, 4, 6132; b) W. U. Huynh, J. J. Dittmer, N. Teclemariam, D. J. Milliron, A. P. Alivisatos, K. W. J. Barnham, *Physical Review B* **2003**, 67, 115326.
- [8] a) Y. Li, X. Li, C. Yang, Y. Li, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2003**, 13, 2641; b) S. Acharya, U. K. Gautam, T. Sasaki, Y. Bando, Y. Golan, K. Ariga, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, 130, 4594; c) D. Placencia, J. E. Boercker, E. E. Foos, J. G. Tischler, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2015**, 6, 3360; d) J. Ning, J. Liu, Y. Levi-Kalisman, A. I. Frenkel, U. Banin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, 140, 14627; e) J. Zhang, S. Jin, H. C. Fry, S. Peng, E. Shevchenko, G. P. Wiederrecht, T. Rajh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, 133, 15324; f) G. Jia, Y. Pang, J. Ning, U. Banin, B. Ji, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, 31, 1900781.
- [9] A. Fu, W. Gu, B. Boussert, K. Koski, D. Gerion, L. Manna, M. Le Gros, C. A. Larabell, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nano Lett.* **2007**, 7, 179.
- [10] a) L.-s. Li, J. Walda, L. Manna, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nano Lett.* **2002**, 2, 557; b) W. Zhang, J. Schneider, V. G. Chigrinov, H. S. Kwok, A. L. Rogach, A. K. Srivastava, *Advanced Optical Materials* **2018**, 6, 1800250.
- [11] H. Htoon, J. A. Hollingworth, A. V. Malko, R. Dickerson, V. I. Klimov, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2003**, 82, 4776.
- [12] R. A. M. Hikmet, P. T. K. Chin, D. V. Talapin, H. Weller, *Adv. Mater.* **2005**, 17, 1436.
- [13] a) W. U. Huynh, J. J. Dittmer, A. P. Alivisatos, *Science* **2002**, 295, 2425; b) A. Salant, M. Shalom, Z. Tachan, S. Buhbut, A. Zaban, U. Banin, *Nano Lett.* **2012**, 12, 2095.
- [14] A. E. Saunders, A. Ghezlbash, P. Sood, B. A. Korgel, *Langmuir* **2008**, 24, 9043.
- [15] G. A. Drake, L. P. Keating, M. Shim, *Chem. Rev.* **2023**, 123, 3761.
- [16] N. D. Bronstein, L. Li, L. Xu, Y. Yao, V. E. Ferry, A. P. Alivisatos, R. G. Nuzzo, *ACS Nano* **2014**, 8, 44.
- [17] a) N. Oh, B. H. Kim, S.-Y. Cho, S. Nam, S. P. Rogers, Y. Jiang, J. C. Flanagan, Y. Zhai, J.-H. Kim, J. Lee, Y. Yu, Y. K. Cho, G. Hur, J. Zhang, P. Trefonas, J. A. Rogers, M. Shim, *Science* **2017**, 355, 616; b) A. Onal, S. Sadeghi, R. Melikov, O. Karatum, G. O. Eren, S. Nizamoglu, *ACS Photonics* **2022**, 9, 3268.
- [18] L. Amirav, A. P. Alivisatos, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, 1, 1051.
- [19] M. T. Sheldon, P.-E. Trudeau, T. Mokari, L.-W. Wang, A. P. Alivisatos, *Nano Lett.* **2009**, 9, 3676.
- [20] C. C. Milleville, E. Y. Chen, K. R. Lennon, J. M. Cleveland, A. Kumar, J. Zhang, J. A. Bork, A. Tessier, J. M. LeBeau, D. B. Chase, J. M. O. Zide, M. F. Doty, *ACS Nano* **2019**, 13, 489.
- [21] a) E. Y. Chen, Z. Li, C. C. Milleville, K. R. Lennon, J. M. O. Zide, M. F. Doty, *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics* **2018**, 8, 746; b) M. Okano, M. Sakamoto, T. Teranishi, Y. Kanemitsu, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, 5, 2951; c) N. N. Hewa-Kasakarage, P. Z. El-

- Khoury, A. N. Tarnovsky, M. Kirsanova, I. Nemitz, A. Nemchinov, M. Zamkov, *ACS Nano* **2010**, 4, 1837; d) L. Carbone, C. Nobile, M. De Giorgi, F. D. Sala, G. Morello, P. Pompa, M. Hytch, E. Snoeck, A. Fiore, I. R. Franchini, M. Nadasan, A. F. Silvestre, L. Chiodo, S. Kudera, R. Cingolani, R. Krahne, L. Manna, *Nano Lett.* **2007**, 7, 2942; e) F. Shieh, A. E. Saunders, B. A. Korgel, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, 109, 8538.
- [22] a) U. Banin, Y. Ben-Shahar, K. Vinokurov, *Chem. Mater.* **2014**, 26, 97; b) H. Schlicke, D. Ghosh, L.-K. Fong, H. L. Xin, H. Zheng, A. P. Alivisatos, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, 52, 980; c) C. O'Sullivan, R. D. Gunning, C. A. Barrett, A. Singh, K. M. Ryan, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2010**, 20, 7875.
- [23] K. Das, S. K. De, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2009**, 113, 3494.
- [24] A. Pareek, P. H. Borse, *Electrochem. Sci. Adv.* **2021**, n/a, e2100114.
- [25] M.-Y. Chen, Y.-J. Hsu, *Nanoscale* **2013**, 5, 363.
- [26] T. L. Nguyen, M. Michael, P. Mulvaney, *Chem. Mater.* **2014**, 26, 4274.
- [27] F. Shieh, A. E. Saunders, B. A. Korgel, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, 109, 8538.
- [28] N. S. Norberg, K. R. Kittilstved, J. E. Amonette, R. K. Kukkadapu, D. A. Schwartz, D. R. Gamelin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, 126, 9387.
- [29] a) L. Zhang, L. Yin, C. Wang, N. lun, Y. Qi, D. Xiang, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2010**, 114, 9651; b) N. S. Norberg, D. R. Gamelin, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, 109, 20810.
- [30] S. Schäfer, Z. Wang, R. Zierold, T. Kipp, A. Mews, *Nano Lett.* **2011**, 11, 2672.
- [31] X. Peng, M. C. Schlamp, A. V. Kadavanich, A. P. Alivisatos, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1997**, 119, 7019.
- [32] S. Kim, B. Fisher, H.-J. Eisler, M. Bawendi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, 125, 11466.
- [33] S. A. Ivanov, A. Piryatinski, J. Nanda, S. Tretiak, K. R. Zavadil, W. O. Wallace, D. Werder, V. I. Klimov, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, 129, 11708.
- [34] A. M. Dennis, M. R. Buck, F. Wang, N. F. Hartmann, S. Majumder, J. L. Casson, J. D. Watt, S. K. Doorn, H. Htoon, M. Sykora, J. A. Hollingsworth, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, 29, 1809111.
- [35] a) A. E. Saunders, B. Koo, X. Wang, C.-K. Shih, B. A. Korgel, *ChemPhysChem* **2008**, 9, 1158; b) K. B. Subila, K. Sandeep, E. M. Thomas, J. Ghatak, S. M. Shivaprasad, K. G. Thomas, *ACS Omega* **2017**, 2, 5150.
- [36] a) I. Das, S. Sagadevan, Z. Z. Chowdhury, N. Vijayan, *J. Mat. Sci.* **2018**, 29, 1600; b) Y. Hao, J. Pei, Y. Wei, Y. Cao, S. Jiao, F. Zhu, J. Li, D. Xu, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2010**, 114, 8622.
- [37] a) V. Srikant, D. R. Clarke, *J. Appl. Phys.* **1998**, 83, 5447; b) V. Srikant, D. R. Clarke, *J. Appl. Phys.* **1997**, 81, 6357.
- [38] B. Carlson, K. Leschkies, E. S. Aydil, X. Y. Zhu, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, 112, 8419.
- [39] R. Li, C. Cai, L. Hu, H. Wu, W. Zhang, J. Zhu, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2013**, 276, 258.
- [40] R. Ehamparam, N. G. Pavlopoulos, M. W. Liao, L. J. Hill, N. R. Armstrong, J. Pyun, S. S. Saavedra, *ACS Nano* **2015**, 9, 8786.
- [41] S. A. Ivanov, M. Achermann, *ACS Nano* **2010**, 4, 5994.
- [42] a) Y. Gao, X. Peng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, 137, 4230; b) L. Jethi, T. G. Mack, P. Kambhampati, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2017**, 121, 26102; c) A. M. Kapitonov, A. P. Stupak, S. V. Gaponenko, E. P. Petrov, A. L. Rogach, A. Eychmüller, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1999**, 103, 10109.
- [43] F. Mirnajafizadeh, D. Ramsey, S. McAlpine, F. Wang, J. A. Stride, *Nanomaterials* **2019**, 9, 465.
- [44] a) A. Haque, M. S. H. Faizi, J. A. Rather, M. S. Khan, *Biorg. Med. Chem.* **2017**, 25, 2017; b) S. Deka, A. Quarta, M. G. Lupo, A. Falqui, S. Boninelli, C. Giannini, G. Morello, M. De Giorgi, G. Lanzani, C. Spinella, R. Cingolani, T. Pellegrino, L. Manna, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, 131, 2948.

